

THE EFFECT OF **GRAPHENE** AS A MULTIFUNCTIONAL ADDITIVE FOR CARBON-FIBER COMPOSITES IN **CRYOGENIC ENVIRONMENTS**

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Hydrogen – Towards **zero-emission** technologies

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Innovation
ZEROe
Towards the world's first hydrogen-powered commercial aircraft

High efficiency

Hydrogen – Towards **zero-emission** technologies

Ultra-light weight hydrogen tanks promises to make jet fuel out of date

Hydrogen – Towards **zero-emission** technologies

- Performing in cryogenic environments (20 K)
- Temperature-swing implies critical thermal stress
- Hydrogen permeates through the CFRP layer
- Microcrack development

Hydrogen storage vessel technology

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- Improves matrix-fiber interaction

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- Reduce matrix-fiber CTE difference

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- Hydrogen barrier properties

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- Hydrogen barrier properties
- Stiffening of the matrix

Hydrogen storage vessel technology

Incorporation of Graphene as a multifunctional additive

Genable® X1400

Genable® 1000

Genable® 1200

Hydrogen storage vessel technology

Genable® X1400

Top-down / Exfoliation

Genable® 1000

**Top-down / Exfoliation
+ oxidized function**

Genable® 1200

Bottom-up / Deposition

Hydrogen storage vessel technology

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Bottom-up / Deposition

Effect of graphene as a multifunctional additive

What is the influence of **graphene** on the manufacturing process of the composite?

Can **graphene** suppress the **CTE** property of the CFRP laminate?

Does **graphene** act as a barrier towards hydrogen permeation?

How will the **graphene** effect the **delamination** process of the CFRP composite

Prepreg Line – Manufacturing of the composite prepregs

Reference

Genable® X1400: 0.1wt

Genable® 1000: 0.1wt

Genable® 1200: 0.1wt

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IM7/EP prepreg 70 gsm fibers

Manufacturing of prepreg laminates

Viscosity measurements of the **Base Resin**

Genable X1400: Minor effect on the resin viscosity with 0.1wt% content

Genable 1000: Minor effect on the resin viscosity with 0.1wt% content

Genable 1200: Significant effect on resin viscosity with 0.1wt% content

Viscosity measurements of the **Base Resin**

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Suitable viscosity and pot-life for Hot-melt prepreg processing → 70-80 °C

Thin ply prepregs possible

Coefficient of thermal expansion CTE

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Hydrogen permeation

der Bundeswehr
Universität München

Hydrogen permeation

der Bundeswehr

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System	Leakage (mbar l s ⁻¹)
Reference	1.1E-6
0.1wt% 1000	9.7E-7
0.1wt% X1400	9.5E-7
0.1wt% 1200	7.5E-7
Commercial M21E	7.7E-8

30%

Interlaminar Energy Release Rate G_{IC}

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Adaptation to 77 K

Interlaminar Energy Release Rate G_{IC}

857 $J m^{-2}$
 783 $J m^{-2}$
 775 $J m^{-2}$
 734 $J m^{-2}$

Decrease in matrix ductility

DIN EN ISO 6033

Load cell: 500 N

Displacement rate: 10 mm min⁻¹

N. of specimens: 5

Carbon-fiber volume content: 56-58vol%

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647 J m⁻²

527 J m⁻²

496 J m⁻²

466 J m⁻²

Decrease in matrix ductility

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The hydrogen permeation of the CFRP laminate **is reduced** by the use of graphene additives

The incorporation of a rigid additive such as graphene, promotes **substantial decrease on the CFRP G_{IC}** , indicating embrittlement and stiffening of the matrix

Tensile properties in cryogenic environments 77 K

Acknowledgements

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